

USE OF GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TERMINOLOGICAL COMPETENCE

Hojiyeva Munavvarkhon Akramovna

NamDU doctoral students

+99891204 95 57

munavvar_qdpi@mail.ru

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Abstract: The issue of terminological competence and linguistic competence is discussed in the article. The use of game technology in the development of terminological competence among philological students and the improvement of terminological competence through it were discussed.

Key words: professional competence, terminological competence, linguistic competence, game technology, term, knowledge, skill, competence.

The development of every country is directly related to education and science. The issue of education is one of the most urgent issues in the development of society. The essence of the educational policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is "To develop our youth as independent thinkers, with high intellectual and spiritual potential, who are not inferior to their peers in any field on a global scale"[1], including the task of training professors and teachers of higher educational institutions who love and appreciate their field, who have advanced knowledge, skills and professional abilities. This shows that the study of issues of development and improvement of terminological competences, which is the core of professional competence in future philological specialists, is relevant.

Terminological competence is the training of a well-rounded person, the understanding of scientific terms, the perfect study of their alternatives, variants and synonyms, as well as their sources of origin, the meaning of terms. Terminological competence is the basis and core of professional competence of philologists. It is desirable for a specialist with terminological competence to learn and collect terms related to his field, learn modern terms and put them into practice. Linguistic and terminological competence is the professional competence of philologist students. "Linguistic competence means the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and competence in the basics of language and its levels: phonetics, lexicon, word structure, word formation, morphology, simple and compound sentence syntax, text style" [2]. If a linguist has an idea about the studied language system and can use it in practice, it can be said that he has linguistic competence.

The use of game technologies gives a good result in the development of terminological competence of philological students in linguistics and literature.

Interactive teaching methods based on games are one of the most effective tools of modern pedagogy.

Before applying the game to educational practice, solving the following pedagogical and psychological issues, every student should know the following:

- The goal of the game;
- The task of the game;
- Which theme of the game is related to the plan;
- To be able to use the skills and abilities formed in the previous games in the next games.

It is necessary to create such technological games as to arouse interest in students, satisfy their needs, and be quickly assimilated by them. Every teacher has a choice when using games, that is, he can choose a game according to the abilities, interests, knowledge and aspirations of his students. Therefore, the use of various games in the lesson of the mother tongue helps students to develop such qualities as speed, sensitivity, determination, mutual respect, speech development, expanding the range of thinking, and responsiveness [3].

Students of the Uzbek language and literature of higher education can use the game "Zakovat" in practical exercises and repeating topics for 5-10 minutes in the course of linguistics and literary studies. During the game, students are divided into two groups. The teacher acts as a leader in the game. Both groups appoint a group leader. The terms selected by the teacher are placed in a large envelope. Group leaders freely choose one of the envelopes. A certain time is set for preparing for the questions. According to the agreement of the group members, one student summarizes the answers of the group members. If one of the group members is not satisfied with the answer, he fills in the answers and explains them. Depending on whether the questions are simple or difficult, the score for the complete answer is written in an envelope in advance.

The second group listens to the answers of the first group, fills in the mistakes and places that need to be explained. The teacher guides, motivates and evaluates the students of the group. Each group divides its points among its members. The participation of group members is taken into account. In this way, students are trained to carefully monitor and evaluate the answers of themselves and their friends. A sense of responsibility and the ability to analyze answers are developed.

Uzbek language and literature 1st level students can organize this game in 10-15 minutes during the practical training of "Uzbek folklore". The use of the "Zakovat" game on the subject of "Folklore genre system and their artistic

features" of this subject arouses students' interest in science. Students' terminological competence will be further strengthened by studying genres related to the science of "Uzbek folklore" or terms related to this science.

Students are divided into two groups. The envelopes are given terms related to Uzbek folklore, Uzbek folklore. For example, the term "Saga". One of the group members will answer about the explanation of this term, its use in classical literature, its characteristics, structure, and types of folk art. For example, "Saga" is an epic genre in the oral works of Turkic peoples. Epics in folklore are large-scale works built on the basis of an eventful plot, performed by bakshi (akin, jirov, manaschi) accompanied by music (dombira, kobiz, etc.), orally – passed through the mouth and reached us. In this process, each performer added something, left something out, and thus the epics were polished. The logical structure of the folk epic is suitable for performance - it alternates between prose and poetic fragments: if the narration is mainly performed in prose, the most important dialogues between the characters, their mental states, descriptions, the performer's attitude, etc., are more poetic. given on the way [4]. Unmentioned places can be filled by group members. (Epics in written and oral literature can provide information about modern epics). The game continues as follows. At the end of the game, the group's accumulated incentives are counted. The winning group will be announced. In this way, terms related to the science will be mastered, explained and strengthened. This develops students' terminological competence, strengthens their memory, and prepares the ground for use in their professional activities. Until the end of the subject, students master several terms, reinforce and repeat the terms they know.

One such memory-enhancing game is the "Lotto" game. This game can be used to reinforce a new topic, to ask questions about a previous topic, as well as for revision lessons.

For this, the teacher puts the numbered balls in a box or bag. You can also write the questions on the board. The teacher takes one of the balls in the box or bag and answers the questions corresponding to the number of the ball in his hand. If there is a word in the number, it will explain it. If the number 1 ball comes out, the number 1 word is explained [5].

This game can be used in the practical exercises of the subject "Modern Uzbek literary language" taught in the 1st stage of the Uzbek language and literature course. During the "Information about phonetics" practical training, the teacher pastes numbers from one to fifteen on the group board. Under the numbers, terms related to the science of "Current Uzbek literary language" will be written.

Students voluntarily choose numbers and interpret the term, justifying their opinions. The rest of the students will hear this answer, they will find other features of the term, and it will be possible to fill in the unmentioned places and aspects. If this game is organized in the reinforcement part of the lesson in 10-15 minutes, the interest in science will increase. For example, if a student chooses the number 3, the word "Phoneme" is given under this number. The student reveals the meaning, explanation, and other aspects of this word.

Phoneme (Greek, phonema - sound). It is the sound shell of language units, a sound unit that has the characteristic of their mutual differentiation. For example, the words "stay", "kil", and "kol" have a sound shell, and the phonemes "o, i, o" serve to distinguish them from each other.

Variant of phoneme. The appearance of a phoneme in the flow of speech under the influence of consonants. The variants of the phoneme do not differentiate the meaning and do not allow the speakers of this language to understand the meaning of the same word. For example, the pronunciation of the "i" sound in the first syllable and the "i" sound in the second syllable of the Uzbek words "bildi" and "ichdi" are not the same. The "i" sound in the words "winter" and "hot" is different from the "i" sound in the words "bildi" and "icdi". But "i" in all of them are variants of one phoneme [6].

When students hear the answer, they can also tell the unspoken places and other ideas about the phoneme term. In this way, it is possible to learn, repeat and master the terms related to the science during the certain allocated time of each lesson. In this way, students' knowledge, skills and competence in using terms will be improved.

Games of this type serve to develop students' terminological competence. Development of terminological competence in students is a guarantee of success. In this case, the effective use of game technologies helps students to work independently and learn terms thoroughly.

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